

Unveiling adsorption processes on H-MOR. A Boltzmann-type distribution model with ONIOM-type calculations

Rodolfo Izquierdo^{1,2*}, Aníbal Sierraalta³, Gustavo Chacón⁴, Hubert Stassen¹

¹ Grupo de Química Teórica, Instituto de Química – UFRGS, Av. Bento Gonçalves 9500, 91540-180 Porto Alegre – RS, Brazil.

² Laboratorio de Química Teórica y Computacional, Departamento de Química, Facultad Experimental de Ciencias, Universidad Del Zulia, Maracaibo, Venezuela.

³ Laboratorio de Química Física y Catálisis Computacional, Centro de Química, Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas, Apartado 21827, Caracas 1020-A, Venezuela.

⁴ Laboratory of Molecular Catalysis, Institute of Chemistry, UFRGS, Av. Bento Gonçalves, 9500, Porto Alegre, RS 91501-970, Brazil.

*E-mail: rodolfo.izquierdo@ufrgs.br, reis131182@gmail.com

Resumen

Comprender la catálisis con H-MOR implica la integración entre diferentes escalas-espacio-tiempo observadas en el reactor. Se sabe que los cálculos ONIOM sólo capturan la dependencia-espacio-temporal sobre sitios activos individuales. Superamos esta limitación combinando cálculos ONIOM(ω B97X:PM6) con modelos de distribución tipo-Boltzmann logrando un modelo de adsorción mejorado. Para probar nuestro modelo, se estudió la interacción de XY=CH₄, CO, CO₂, CH₃OH y (CH₃)₂O con H-MOR. Los valores-promedio calculados para el calor de adsorción ($\langle\Delta H_a\rangle$) concuerdan con los valores experimentales. No siempre el sitio ácido de Brønsted que interactúa más fuertemente con XY ($\langle\Delta H_a\rangle \ll 0$) es el sitio activo que predomina en el reactor.

Palabras clave: cálculos-ONIOM, distribución tipo-Boltzmann, H-MOR, adsorción, catálisis.

Abstract

Understanding catalysis with H-MOR involves integration between different space-time-scales observed at the reactor. It is known that ONIOM calculations only can well capture space-time-dependent phenomena at individual active sites. We overcome this limitation by combining ONIOM(ω B97X:PM6) calculations with Boltzmann-type distribution models to improve the adsorption model. The interaction of XY=CH₄, CO, CO₂, CH₃OH, and (CH₃)₂O with H-MOR was studied to test our model. The calculated average-values for the heat of adsorption ($\langle\Delta H_a\rangle$) agree with the experimental values. It is not always true that Brønsted acid site that interacts more strongly with XY ($\langle\Delta H_a\rangle \ll 0$) is active site that predominates in reactor.

Keywords: ONIOM-calculations, Boltzmann-type distribution, H-MOR, adsorption, catalysis.

Highlights

ONIOM-DFT calculations and a statistical thermodynamic model to estimate experimental adsorptions heats are presented.

Percentage of Al³⁺ and average vibrations of BASs calculated with the distribution explained the experimental data available for the H-MOR.

Based on the adsorption model, XY preferably interacts with the O7-containing BAS.

The average adsorption heats calculated ($\langle\Delta H_a\rangle$) are consistent with experimental data available.

Graphical Abstract

Introduction

The fundamental understanding of how surfaces catalyze a chemical reaction is an essential component to develop new heterogeneous catalysts (HCs). A successful heterogeneous catalytic reaction is governed by three fundamental elementary steps, namely adsorption (A), surface reactions (SR), and desorption (D), associated with a solid surface. Several theoretical and experimental investigations have particularly taken up Sabatier's principle's simple and elegant idea to correlate the adsorption heats (ΔH_a) with HCs [1–3]. Therefore, at the theoretical level, the precise calculation of ΔH_a is a current topic.

To create a comprehensive theoretical description of ΔH_a it is necessary to consider the multiscale problem that stems from the different characteristic time and length scales of the different adsorption processes on the solid under the experimental conditions [4]. Both periodic and cluster-finite calculations only can well capture space- and time-dependent adsorption phenomena at the level of isolated active sites (atoms: $< 10^3$; lengths: 10^{-10} to 10^{-9} m; time: $\sim 10^{-12}$ s) [5]. On the other hand, molecular dynamics and Monte Carlo calculations lead to more flexible adsorption models (atoms: $< 10^6$ lengths: 10^{-8} to 10^{-7} m; time: $\sim 10^{-9}$ s). However, their sites distribution and adsorption models are not precise and neglect the adsorption modes that activate chemical bonds [6]. Furthermore, using a single theoretical approach is not always enough, and the coupling between different models is required. Therefore, particular theoretical efforts need to be developed for the integration of different time and length scales.

HCs based on acidic zeolites (H-Z) such as the protonic mordenite (H-MOR) is one key example where the complexity of heterogeneous catalysis involves the integration between different time and length scales observed in catalytic reactions at the reactor level. Usually, H-MOR is characterized by a high heterogeneity of potentially adsorption sites in their micropores. Furthermore, with time it became clear that very often, H-Z with defects in corners and edges of crystals provide changes in both adsorption and catalytic activities, i.e., the H-MOR system is more heterogeneous than expected [2].

The H-MOR unit cell contains four (4) non-equivalent crystallographic tetrahedral sites (T = Si or Al atoms) where Si^{4+} can exchange with Al^{3+} to generate a Brønsted site, usually called T_n (with n=1-4, see Figure 1).

Figure 1. MOR zeolite framework: a) viewed along the c-axis, and b) viewed along the b-axis. T1-T4 and O1-O10 indicate four and ten non-equivalent crystallographic sites of Al and O atoms, respectively.

Additionally, according to the notation suggested by the International Zeolite Association (IZA), H-MOR presents ten (10) non-equivalent crystallographic oxygens, usually called O_m (with m=1-10) where Brønsted acid sites (BAS) can be generated. Therefore, under H-MOR synthesis conditions, the H⁺ can be located in the fourteen (14) different T_nO_m crystallographic positions described in Figure 1, to produce 14 BAS per unit cell in the H-MOR (M-T_n-O_m-H). For T_nO_m positions, several possible H⁺ locations could exist. For example, in T4O9, H⁺ could be located around 4-MR-pore (M-T4-O9-H) (Figure 1a)) or in the opposite, around 5-MR-pore (M-T4-O9-H) (Figure 1b).

This structural characteristic produces dynamic changes in the nature, distribution, and accessibility of active sites and their adsorption and catalytic properties.

Using experimental techniques such as FTIR, ²⁷Al-NMR, elemental analysis, and X-ray, the relationship between the Al³⁺ incorporated in the T_n sites for a "perfect" purely acidic H-MOR has been determined [7]. It is reported that the Al³⁺ distributions generated by Monte Carlo methods differ widely from the experimental data for acidic zeolites such as H-MOR. At the theoretical level, it is possible to obtain relative stability for the exchange of Si⁴⁺ by Al³⁺ [7,8]. However, the conclusions of these studies are generally contradictory, which justifies the development of new Al³⁺

distribution models that give a more realistic and less random explanation of the isomorphic substitution process in H-MOR.

Proton localization in the H-MOR is still a subject of broad debate. However, the experimental FTIR spectrum of the H-MOR presents a band located at 3609 cm^{-1} with bandwidth ($\Delta\omega$) of 40 cm^{-1} , attributed to OH stretching vibrations of the BAS (ν_{OH}). The typical deconvolution produces two single bands, with the maxima around 3585 cm^{-1} and 3612 cm^{-1} . These two signals, termed low frequency (LF) and high frequency (HF) bands, correspond to the BASs located in the secondary (i.e., 8-MR, 5MR, and 4-MR) and primary (i.e., 12-MR) channels, respectively [9]. Conversely, other band assignments have been reported for the FTIR of H-MOR [10], this fact and the mobility evidence of the H^+ in H-MOR [11,12], remarks the viewpoint in which experimental observations such as vibrations (ν_{OH}) or deprotonation energy (EDP), represent an ensemble average over many molecules or sites and often a superposition of different reactions. For clarity, see the physicochemical processes on T1 sites in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. An XY probe's adsorption process on the four possible BASs located at position T1 in the H-MOR (M-T1-Om-H). A similar process occurs at the T2, T3, and T4 sites.

The molecular adsorption on H-MOR occurs through a more heterogeneous process than expected, experimental measurements of ΔH_a represent a temporal average of local variations in different adsorption modes and different sites (BAS), as well as in different regions in the solid that may contain terminal silanol groups ($-\text{O}_3\text{SiOH}$), where there may be simultaneous adsorptions. Therefore, by using different types of probe molecules, such as CH_4 , CO , CO_2 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , CH_3OH , and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}$, NH_3 , and

pyridine ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, Py), it is common to obtain ΔH_a values in wide ranges from a Temperature-Programmed Desorption (TPD) and calorimetry experiments [13–16]. Also, the ΔH_a values usually decrease with increasing H-MOR coverage, indicating different types of BAS with different acid forces (EDP) during adsorption [17,18]. Nevertheless, despite advances in the precise calculation for ΔH_a at a theoretical level, this fact is neglected by most publications [19].

Herein, we propose a new adsorption model to probe molecules on H-MOR using ONIOM calculations ($\omega\text{B97X:PM6}$) combined with Boltzmann-type distribution models. Our model manages to correctly describe a more ample space or time scale phenomena in this microporous material with particular catalytic interest, e.g., Al^{3+} distribution, BAS location, FTIR band, and experimental ΔH_a .

Computational Procedure and Theoretical Background.

All calculations were carried out by using the GAUSSIAN-2009 (G09) program [20] and ONIOM two-layer methodology (ONIOM2). The semi-empirical schemes PM6 for the low-level and DFT (ωB97X) for the high-level calculations were employed [21]. We utilized the pseudopotential LanL2DZ defined for Si, Al, H, and O atoms present in the high-level region and the basis set 6-311++G(d,p) for H, C, O, N and S atoms present in the probe molecules (XY): CH_4 , N_2 , CO , CO_2 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , CH_3OH , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}$, H_2S , and CH_3SH molecules. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by two factors developed in our group: 0.9478 and 0.9540 for ν_{OH} and ν_{XY} , respectively. Thermodynamic property calculations (free energy (ΔG°) and enthalpy (ΔH°)) were performed at 298 K and 673 K.

In the unit cell of H-MOR, there are fourteen (14) different positions where the BAS can be generated (M-Tn-Om-H, see Figure 1). Therefore, to represent the H-MOR, we designed a two-layer ONIOM model used with 27 tetrahedrons (TO4, with T = Si or Al) for the model system and 166 tetrahedrons for the actual system (27T, 166T, see Figure 2).

Figure 2. BAS model in site M-T4-O10-H: a) Definition of the actual model ONIOM2 (166T), and b) Definition of the high-level ONIOM2 (27T).

A good starting point is to develop a statistical thermodynamic model for Al^{3+} distribution and BAS location based on Boltzmann-type distribution. Under the H-MOR synthesis, the H^+ can be located in the fourteen (14) different TnOm crystallographic positions described in Figure 1.

Additionally, only two possible conformations were studied for the BAS located between two adjacent 5-MR rings in H-MOR, denoted M-T2-O6-H(a), and M-T2-O6-H(b). Finally, the four possible conformations M-T3-O9-H(a), M-T3-O9-H(b), M-T4-O9-H(a), M-T4-O9-H(b), were studied to produce 17 BAS per unit cell that represent our initial ensemble. When calculating the different BASs using ONIOM2, a distribution is produced according to the Boltzmann-populations:

Table 1. ΔH_s , dE, $B_{n,mH}$ y $\%P_{(298,15K)}$ y EDP calculated at 673.15 K for all the BAS in H-MOR.

Model	dE ^a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_s (kcal mol ⁻¹)	EDP (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ν_{OH} (cm ⁻¹)	$B_{n,mH}$	$\%P_{(298,15K)}$
M-T1-O1-H	1.6	-55.5	347.9	3641	3.1×10^{-1}	9.6×10^0
M-T1-O2-H	3.9	-52.9	344.8	3642	5.5×10^{-2}	1.7×10^0
M-T1-O3-H	7.6	-50.5	341.9	3653	3.3×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-1}
M-T1-O4-H	5.1	-52.3	343.3	3625	2.2×10^{-2}	6.8×10^{-1}
M-T2-O4-H	2.1	-55.2	342.9	3649	2.1×10^{-1}	6.7×10^0
M-T2-O5-H	1.2	-55.2	344.3	3628	4.1×10^{-1}	12.9×10^0
M-T2-O6-H(a)	10.2	-50.0	337.0	3354	4.9×10^{-4}	1.5×10^{-2}
M-T2-O6-H(b)	11.3	-48.9	335.8	3139	2.1×10^{-4}	6.7×10^{-3}
M-T2-O7-H	4.5	-52.0	340.3	3642	3.5×10^{-2}	1.1×10^0
M-T3-O3-H	2.9	-55.3	343.5	3636	1.1×10^{-1}	3.5×10^0
M-T3-O8-H	0.3	-56.1	345.2	3603	7.8×10^{-1}	24.7×10^0
M-T3-O9-H(a)	8.3	-52.2	340.2	3421	2.1×10^{-3}	6.5×10^{-2}
M-T3-O9-H(b)	7.7	-53.1	340.7	2858	3.2×10^{-3}	9.9×10^{-2}
M-T4-O7-H	2.1	-54.5	342.2	3638	2.1×10^{-1}	6.7×10^0
M-T4-O9-H(a)	8.0	-55.2	338.6	3397	2.9×10^{-2}	9.1×10^{-1}
M-T4-O9-H(b)	11.9	-48.0	334.7	3088	1.4×10^{-4}	4.4×10^{-3}
M-T4-O10-H	0.0	-56.3	345.4	3581	1.0×10^0	31.5×10^0
		-55.7 ± 0.4^b	344.9 ± 1.2^c	$3608 \pm 41^{d,e}$	$Z = 3.1775^f$	

^adE: relative energy for M-Tn-Om-H models. ^bGeneral average values for ΔH_s of all BAS ($\langle \Delta H_s \rangle_g$). $\langle \Delta H_s \rangle_g = \sum_{k=1}^{17} P_{(673.15K,k)} \cdot \Delta H_{s,k}$ and standard deviation ($\sigma(\Delta H_s)_g$). $\sigma(\Delta H_s)_g = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{17} P_{(673.15K,k)} \cdot (\Delta H_{s,k} - \langle \Delta H_s \rangle_g)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. ^cAcid force defined as general average values for EDP ($\langle EDP \rangle_g \pm \sigma(\langle EDP \rangle_g)$). ^d $\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle_g \pm \sigma(\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle_g)$. ^eExperimental values: $\nu_{OH} = 3609 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\Delta\omega = 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [22]. ^fNormalization constant of the distribution. $Z = \sum_{k=1}^{17} B_{n,mH,k} = \sum_{k=1}^{17} e^{-\frac{E_{M-Tn-Om-H(k)}}{kT}}$

$$P_{(T,i)} = \frac{B_{n,mHi}}{Z} = \frac{e^{-\frac{E_{M-Tn-Om-Hi}}{kT}}}{\sum_{k=1}^{17} e^{-\frac{E_{M-Tn-Om-H(k)}}{kT}}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\%P_{(T,i)} = P_{(T,i)} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

It is interesting to propose that the $\%P_{(T,K)}$ values calculated from Eq. 2 represent the expected amount of BAS in the H-MOR. Furthermore, adding the $P_{(T,K)}$ for each site Tn ($\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(Tn)$) could estimate the experimental Al^{3+} distribution in H-MOR. The Al^{3+} distribution and BAS amount per Tn site are values that can easily be obtained from experiments [7].

On the other hand, for a Boltzmann-type distribution the average value ($\langle X \rangle$) for property X can be calculated with Eq. 3 and its standard deviation with Eq. 4.

$$\langle X \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N P_{T,i} \cdot X_i \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\sigma(\langle X \rangle) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N P_{T,i} (X_i - \langle X \rangle)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

We could calculate the average values for the deprotonation energy (EDP, reaction in Eq. 5), isomorphous substitution enthalpy (ΔH_s , reaction in Eq. 6) or O-H stretching vibrations of BASs (ν_{OH}). The $\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle$ values will be compared with the H-MOR experimental FTIR, which allows us to validate our model.

Table 2. Performance of our Al³⁺ distribution model by using ONIOM2 calculations vs. published calculations.

Authors	T	$\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(T1)^a$	$\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(T2)$	$\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(T3)$	$\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(T4)$
Iglesia <i>et al.</i> [23] ^b	298.15	68.0	1.8	28.8	2.2
	433.15	63.2	4.8	27.7	7.7
	673.15	58.6	9.8	23.9	1.9
Guo <i>et al.</i> [24] ^b	298.15	15.9	60.0	9.8	14.9
	673.15	25.1	42.1	14.4	18.5
Bucko <i>et al.</i> [25] ^b	298.15	23.0	39.0	21.9	15.7
	673.15	28.2	29.0	23.7	19.1
This work	298.15	5.0	10.0	31.6	52.9
	673.15	12.1	20.7	28.2	39.0
		% T1	% T2	% T3	% T4
Lukyanov <i>et al.</i> [7] ^d	EXP ^d	11.5	24.5	24.9	39.1

^a DFT-periodic calculations. ^d Experimental Al³⁺ distribution from ref. [7,26].

Tabla 3. Outstanding results of adsorption model of probe molecules on H-MOR at 298.15 K.

XY-H-MOR	N ^b	Z ^c	$\sum \text{TnOm}_{(90\%P_{(298.15K)})} > 90\% ^d$	$\langle \Delta H_a \rangle_g ^e$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta(\Delta H_a)^f$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$\langle v_{OH} \rangle_g ^g$ (cm ⁻¹)	Δv_{OH}^h (cm ⁻¹)	ΔR^i (cm ⁻¹)
N ₂ -H-MOR	11	2.7447	T2O5, T3O8, T4O7	-3.5±0.8	-2.1	3529±39	-19	79
CH ₄ -H-MOR	11	1.9688	T2O5, T1O1, T4O7	-5.5±0.6	-0.4	3481±58	-	127
CO-H-MOR	11	3.1215	T4O10, T2O4, T4O7	-6.5±1.2	-0.4	3287±69	0	321
CO ₂ -H-MOR	11	1.2551	T2O7, T4O7	-8.6±0.9	-1.1	3398±28	-	210
C ₂ H ₄ -H-MOR	11	1.9498	T4O7, T2O4, T2O5, T2O7	-12.1±0.8	2.4	3191±41	-	417
H ₂ S-H-MOR	11	1.0291	T2O7	-18.1±1.0	-	2824±25	-	784
O(CH ₃) ₂ -H-MOR	11	1.6317	T4O10, T4O7, T2O5	-23.3±0.7	2.5	2184±83	-	1424
CH ₃ OH-H-MOR	11	1.0016	T4O7	-23.7±0.2	0.0	1648±10	-	1960

^k is a number associated with XY on the graph of $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle = m |\Delta R_{\text{expl}}|^{1/2} + b$. ^bN is the number of accessible states. ^cZ is the normalization constant. ^d $\sum \text{TnOm}_{(90\%P_{(298.15K)})}$ indicates the TnOm sites that group more than 90 % of XY adsorptions on H-MOR. ^e $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle_g \pm \sigma(\Delta H_a)_g$. ^f $\Delta(\Delta H_a) = (\Delta H_{a(\text{EXP})} - \langle \Delta H_a \rangle_g)$. ^g $\langle v_{OH} \rangle_g \pm \sigma(\langle v_{OH} \rangle_g)$. ^h $\Delta v_{OH} = v_{OH(\text{EXP})} - \langle v_{OH} \rangle_g$. ⁱ $\Delta R = \langle v_{OH} \rangle_{g(\text{BAS})} - \langle v_{OH} \rangle_{g(\text{XY-BAS})}$

Discussion

1. Al³⁺ distribution and BAS location based on one Boltzmann-type distribution.

Table 1 shows the ΔH_s results for the isomorphous substitution (reaction in Eq. 6) and the relative stability of BASs formed (M-Tn-Om-H, dE). The exchange of Si⁴⁺ by Al³⁺ is exothermic in any position (TnOm); however, a most exothermic reaction occurs in T4O10 position located in the main channel (12-MR), and the least exothermic occurs in T2O6 position located in the 5-MR channel. However, these results do not agree with the previous locations published at the theoretical level by different authors who use different models and methodologies, e.g., O1, O3, O5 and O7 [24]; O3, O4 and O9 [27]; O4 and O7 [28]; O7, O3 and O1 [25]. On the other hand, dE values indicate that the most stable BAS were: M-T4-O10-H, M-T3-O8-H, M-T2-O5-H, and M-T1-

O1-H; three of those BAS is located in 12-MR channel, and only M-T3-O8-H is located in 8-MR channel. dE values lead to preferential locations of the H⁺ on the Om positions: O1, O5, O8, and O10. Thus, there are discrepancies between the results published and the dE values in Table 1. At the theoretical level, the preferential positions for both Al³⁺ and BAS depend on different electronic environments of Om in the unit cell, and the model and selected methodology. It must be demonstrated if our H-MOR model responds to available experimental data. Table 2 shows the $\sum \%P_{(T,K)}(Tn)$ values estimated with the proposed Boltzmann-type distribution model and by combining ONIOM2 calculations (this work) and other published DFT-periodic calculations.

Our results indicate that when increasing T from 298.15 to 673.15 K, i.e., at synthesis conditions, thermal energy permits population of state that were significantly less accessible at

298.15 K. Thus, there is an increase in the Al^{3+} amount in the T1 and T2 positions at the expense of an Al^{3+} redistribution in the T4 and T3 positions. Conversely to the results produced from the published DFT-periodic calculations (see Table 2), our theoretical Al^{3+} distribution at 673.15 K is very similar to the experimental Al^{3+} distribution for a "perfect" purely acidic H-MOR [7].

During the synthesis of H-MOR, see reaction in Eq. 6, can co-occur in all accessible positions TnOm according to the $\%P_{(673,15,K)}$ incorporating H^+ to H-MOR is more likely in BAS: M-T4-O10-H, M-T3-O8-H, M-T2-O5-H, M-T1-O1-H, and O10, O8, O5, and O1 concentrate over 76.2 % of protonations in the H-MOR. These positions coincide with the obtained experimentally by Martucci *et al.* [29] (O3, O5, O8, and O10) and Alberti [8] (O1, O4, and O8). Finally, $\%P_{(673,15,K)}$ values seem to indicate that the most unstable BASs located in the 4-MR and 5-MR channels (e.g., M-T4-O9-H (b)) are produced in a very low quantity (<1%), but these sites are the most acidic (see EDP in Table 1). Thus, our model confirms the experimental idea that the strongest acid sites are most difficult to form and their concentration is the lowest among all acid sites. In this work, we use a Gaussian-type function to reproduce IR intensities in the zone corresponding to ν_{OH} band located at 3609 cm^{-1} and it is decomposition in BAF (3612 cm^{-1}) and BBF (3585 cm^{-1}), respectively. For clarity, see Figure 3a with the experimental FTIR spectrum for H-MOR. The strategy to simulate the experimental bands is based on: (i) use of the general Boltzmann-type distribution from Table 1 for all accessible BAS before deconvolution ($N=17$, $Z=3.1775$); (ii) use the general average value and it is the standard deviation ($\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle_g \pm \sigma(\nu_{OH})_g$) to simulate the experimental band at 3609 cm^{-1} with $\Delta\omega$ of 40 cm^{-1} . Following the analysis for the decomposition of experimental bands, according to Makanova *et al.* [22], $\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle$ were calculated for BAS located in 12-MR channel ($\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle_{12-MR}$) and those BAS located in secondary channels ($\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle_{sec}$). These last values of $\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle$ were used to determine the experimental bands BAF and BBF, respectively (see Figure 3b).

Figure 3. ν_{OH} -zone simulation of FTIR spectrum for H-MOR: a) Experimental, and b) Theoretical.

Particularly, we established two Boltzmann-type distribution compatible with spectral deconvolution according to Makanova *et al.* [22], the first ensemble, groups seven accessible states for M-Tn-Om-H located in main channels (12-MR, $N=7$, and $Z=2.1895$), the second ensemble, groups ten accessible states for M-Tn-Om-H located in secondary channels (4-MR, 5-MR and 8-MR, $N=10$ and $Z=1.2601$).

Finally, we were able to simulate other band deconvolution models (3609 cm^{-1}) with a higher experimental resolution by using ONIOM calculations with different ensembles, e.g., one decomposition in three bands (3610 cm^{-1} , 3605 cm^{-1} , and 3585 cm^{-1}) by Marie *et al.* [30], as well as the decomposition in six bands (3625 cm^{-1} , 3617 cm^{-1} , 3610 cm^{-1} , 3600 cm^{-1} , 3590 cm^{-1} and 3582 cm^{-1}) by Lukyanov *et al.* [10].

The results indicate that increasing the resolution of the IR experiments requires narrow and refined ensembles, i.e., N values minors, so, when reaching the maximum resolution in the experiments that allow direct visualization of each BAS, the number of decomposition bands should be around 14, which is the maximum number of different TnOm positions. While best experimental

models tend to look at smaller space-time scales, best theoretical models tend to look at bigger ones; from our perspective, those are the right directions towards the perfect modeling.

2. Adsorption model of probe molecules on H-MOR.

The new adsorption model's development consists of XY interaction with all possible accessible positions (TnOm) in H-MOR. However, it is evident that due to structural limitations, most XY probes do not interact with TnOm positions located in the secondary channels (4-MR and 5-MR). For clarity, Figure 4 shows the ONIOM high-level for all CO interactions with H-MOR. Table 3 summarizes the results provided by the statistical model of adsorptions. $\sum TnOm(\%P_{(298.15K)})$ indicates the selectivity in the adsorption on H-MOR, it is observed that independently of the XY probe, only a few BAS were important in the adsorption process.

Figure 4. Structures optimized with ω B97X:PM6 for CO interaction with TnOm positions: (a) (a) T1O1; (b) T1O2; (c) T1O3; (d) T1O4; (e) T2O4; (f) T2O5; (g) T2O7; (h) T3O3; (i) T3O8; (j) T4O7; (k) T4O10.

The $\%P_{(298.15K)}$ values seem to indicate that positions with O7 were common in almost all the adsorption processes studied. Furthermore, for all XY probes studied, the TnOm site where the most exothermic adsorption occurs ($\Delta H_a \ll$) is not included in $\sum TnOm(\%P_{(298.15K)}) > 90\%$. Particularly, the XY probes that interact mainly by hydrogen bonding with H-MOR tend to develop very selective adsorption processes.

We believe that this finding could be of interest for developing new HCs for catalytic processes of great importance, such as capture and conversion of H_2S , conversion of Methanol To Hydrocarbons (MTH), or the conversion of Methyl Mercaptan To Hydrocarbons (M2TH). Considering the results, the development of new materials rich in BAS type TnO7 is of great interest and relevance.

Finally, Figure 5 shows the linear fit between $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle$ and ΔR of $\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle$ after XY adsorption on H-MOR.

Figure 5. Plot of $|\Delta R|^{1/2}$ vs. $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle$. Model according to Wakabayashi *et al.* [31], $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle = m |\Delta R|^{1/2} + b$ ($m = -0.6003 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1/2}$, y $b = 0.4707 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $r^2 = 0,9469$).

Wakabayashi *et al.* [31] previously published this linear model experimentally for the O_2 , N_2 , and Ar adsorptions on H-MOR, so this double validation allows proposing magnitudes of $\langle \Delta H_a \rangle$ very similar to experimental values. We present our theoretical model as a robust alternative for the calculation of ΔH_a in probes challenging to manipulate (e.g., H_2S and CH_3SH). In addition, it is helpful in cases where the probes react very quickly with the BAS (e.g., C_2H_6 and C_3H_6).

Conclusions

ONIOM-DFT calculations and a statistical thermodynamic model to estimate experimental adsorptions heats were successfully examined. The $\% Al^{3+}$ and average O-H stretching vibrations of BASs ($\langle \nu_{OH} \rangle$) calculated with the statistical distribution were able to explain the experimental data available for one "perfect" pure H-MOR. In our adsorption model, XY probes preferably interact with the O7-containing BAS. The calculated average adsorption heats are consistent with available experimental results. Therefore, the described

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theoretical model constitutes an outstanding and helpful tool for the calculation of ΔH_a in challenging and reactive probes.

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